

InvestCEC

Summary of Support and Facilitation Measures and Activities - End of Project

Venionaire Capital AG

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Full term / explanation
AIF	Alternative Investment Fund
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CE	Circular Economy
CVF	Carinthian Venture Fund
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (European Commission)
EC	European Commission
EIC	European Innovation Council
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
EU	European Union
EuVECA	European Venture Capital Funds (label/regime)
FoF	Fund of Funds
G!E	Greenovate! Europe
G2G	Gate2Growth
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IR	Investor Readiness
KPI	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LP	Limited Partner
MAT	MATERIALIA
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NCP	National Contact Point (EIC/EC network)
PPP	Public–Private Partnership
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
STW-AG	Stadtwerke Klagenfurt Aktiengesellschaft
UI	User Interface
VC	Venture Capital
VENCAP	Venionaire Capital AG

1. Introduction and background

1.1. Brief overview of the main task (T3.3) and its objectives

Task T3.3 delivers InvestCEC's support and facilitation layer for cities, regions, and entrepreneurs, enabling them to initiate, de-risk, and replicate circular-economy projects. MATERIALIA (MAT) was the lead for T3.3 from the project's start until its beneficiary termination on 29 November 2024. Throughout this period, the consortium collectively contributed to the development of replication assets and the operation of practical interfaces, engaging founders, utilities, and investors. Following MAT's exit, VENCAP formally assumed the lead and carried T3.3 to completion, continuing the same work plan with the wider consortium. VENCAP was well positioned to assume the lead role, drawing on its track record in venture and private-equity investing, technology valuation, corporate-startup collaboration, and alternative fund management. VENCAP was also the partner which most actively supported MAT on the replication task and plan. The objectives of T3.3 consisted of three parts:

1. **Building knowledge and capacity** so that municipal actors and founders can translate needs into investable, utility-ready pilots (through guides, templates, factsheets, and webinar training aligned with the demonstration activities).
2. **Creating visibility and matching** via a public **website, Marketplace** and PR that profiles relevant solutions and routes stakeholders towards contact, coaching, and pilot design.
3. **Identifying and securing funding** by scanning public and private instruments and **matching opportunities to projects** through InvestCEC's investment programme, which resulted in a fully documented fund set-up ready for establishment and a venture-partnership ("virtual fund") that enables co-investment before and alongside first close.

How the objectives were implemented: in practice, the **project website**, when relevant, seconded by the InvestCEC Zenodo community, served as the open repository for public deliverables, guides, and replication materials and hosted the **InvestCEC Marketplace**. The team pivoted the community exchange from a stand-alone forum to **LinkedIn** (complemented by website contact flows), which proved more effective for founder and municipal engagement and for channelling discussions linked to webinars, calls for entrepreneurs, and policy sessions.

- **T3.3.1 – Capacity building and stakeholder support:** delivered reusable resources (factsheets, templates, investor and utility checklists), **webinars** with CCRI peers, and an embedded discussion channel (LinkedIn and website contact), replacing the low-traction platform while preserving the intent to facilitate exchange.

- **T3.3.3 – Monitoring and seizing funding opportunities:** Conducted continuous **scouting of public and private finance** and **matched them** to the project pipeline (two Calls for Entrepreneurs plus VENCAP's deal flow). This activity fed into the **investment programme** (Alternative Investment Fund materials; **venture-partnership “virtual fund”**), enabling co-investments with aligned managers and strategic partners.

Together, actions under these tasks established a reusable pathway from **needs → pilot design → funding match → deployment**, providing a model that other cities and regions can readily adopt.

1.2. Methodology

This deliverable documents how the consortium engaged stakeholders, communicated progress, and strengthened ties with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI). Partners coordinated through a consistent rhythm of project meetings, thematic working sessions, and targeted bilateral calls to resolve technical or organisational issues. A shared coordination framework kept all parties aligned on activities, webinars, milestones, and events, while ensuring that materials (guides, templates, recordings) remained accessible for replication.

Engagement was further supported by continuous internal feedback of project partners and by external inputs, primarily from dissemination events of CCRI and CIRN events that project partners participated in. These inputs were synthesised into periodic snapshots summarizing outreach results, lessons learned, and follow-up actions. The process helped identify good practices (e.g., where CCRI channels and partner networks outperformed generic outreach) and pinpointed areas for improvement that directly informed updates to the selection criteria, investment-readiness process, and event formats.

Together, these collaboration and communication measures enhanced the quality of stakeholder interactions, deepened CCRI integration, and contributed to the project's replication objectives.

2. Knowledge, Confidence and Capacity Building

The CCRI is a European Commission (EC) initiative launched by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) as part of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan (2020). Since its inception, the CCRI has made a significant contribution to advancing policy objectives related to sustainable growth and reducing the environmental footprint of economic activities within the European Union (EU). Its activities directly support the goals of the European Green Deal and the EU Bioeconomy Strategy.

From its genesis back in 2020, the CCRI has been actively involved, not only in creating a community of practice designed to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among a wide range of stakeholders from across the **quadruple helix** (cities, regions, industry representatives, research and technology organisations, and civil society), but also supporting the funding and uptake of a diverse range of projects aimed at embedding and expanding the principles of CE, transforming it into a mainstream and widely adopted practice throughout Europe's cities and regions.

Funding has been allocated to initiatives such as InvestCEC, which are designed to facilitate the shift towards a CE within European cities and regions by creating a model that uses the city of Klagenfurt as a test bed; the latter, being a pioneer, should produce results with a potential for replicability across different EU cities and regions. To achieve this, InvestCEC has been committed to fostering replication by providing valuable information and resources to a broad audience cities, local and regional governments, stakeholders and individuals interested in sustainable development and circular economy practices. In this manner, content materials, documentation, and activities, undertaken by the project that can be used for replication, will not only be openly accessible through the project's website and additional platforms (e.g., Horizon Europe Results Platform, CCRI Intranet, relevant partner repositories, and the InvestCEC Zenodo community), but also will be actively promoted and disseminated to ensure broader visibility and uptake by VENCAP and STW-AG further.

2.1. Resource page

The InvestCEC website served as the public, one-stop hub for replication, hosting approved public deliverables, practical guides and templates, webinar recordings, and the Marketplace of solutions. Greenovate! Europe (G!E) managed communications, brand assets, and publishing workflows. MAT led replication content until its beneficiary termination (29 Nov 2024); after which the consortium continued under VENCAP's coordination to curate the end-of-project resource set (selection and investment-readiness materials, public-private partnership (PPP)/off-take templates, investor guidance), in line with the agreed Replication plan.

Website Organisation

- **Communication Tools:** visual identity, logo kit, and usage guidelines curated by G!E.
- **Press & Media:** press releases and media items (project kick-off, Calls for Entrepreneurs, events) coordinated jointly by VENCAP, G2G, Enspire, G!E, CARTIF.
- **Public Deliverables:** EC-approved project results in form of public deliverables; deliverables awaiting validation are marked Draft. Each file card shows version/date and a short status note.
- **Replication Materials:** practical, “ready-to-use” templates and guides for cities, utilities and founders.
- **Webinars & Recordings:** on-demand training sessions with slides and direct links to referenced tools.
- **Policy & Replication:** policy workshop outputs and concise replication briefs, cross-linked to CCRI and Horizon Results Platform entries, when relevant.
- **Marketplace:** solution profiles in a standardised format (focus area, maturity, CE/impact, investment need, contacts) plus a lightweight **helpdesk intake** (contact form) for regions, cities and utilities seeking follow-up support.

Public Deliverables (selection)

- **D2.1 Model and tools for urban/regional circular economy projects — V1.** Detailed explanation of the InvestCEC model and its four stages: needs definition, entrepreneur solutions, business case/plan, and application of the investment programme.
- **D2.3 Report on a model for initiation and implementation of circular economy projects — Initial version.** Progress overview for the first year of model development and demonstration (M6–M12).
- **D3.2 Circular economy investments — Financial barriers and potential measures.** Analysis of financing obstacles (upfront costs, risk/return uncertainty, instrument gaps) and countermeasures (tailored instruments, PPPs, incentives, investor education).

Replication materials

A comprehensive, ready-to-use package enables cities and regions to adopt the InvestCEC model. It includes:

- The European Replication Plan and a **National Replication Guide (DE)** as the hands-on guidebook, distilling the exact steps to run **needs → selection → IR → pilot** with governance and procurement notes.

- **Step-by-step manuals & templates.** Entrepreneur **sourcing** and **selection** (two-gate funnel, scoring rubric, interview guide, **Marketplace profile template**); **investment-readiness**; and **PPP deployment**.
- **Funding resources.** **Fundraising Guidebook** (what investors look for, traction/Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), raise sizing, term-sheet basics); **Monitoring Investment Opportunities** (how to combine grants/loans/mezzanine/equity and use off-take/guarantees to improve bankability); and an **investment-programme info pack** (focus & facts of the **AIF fund**, ready for establishment, and the **venture-partnership (“virtual fund”)** pathway enabling co-investments before and alongside first close).
- **Education & training.** **Webinars & recordings**, slide decks, and short policy/replication briefs for cities, entrepreneurs, and investors, designed to accelerate practical adoption.

Operational updates:

- **Status & versioning:** each item shows **Public/Draft** status, version/date, and, where applicable, persistent links (e.g., Zenodo/Horizon Results Platform) for long-term access.
- **Quick-access cards:** pinned **Replication Pack**, **Webinars & Recordings**, and **Policy & Replication** cards help users find the most actionable items first.
- **Clarity for users:** file cards indicate the primary work package (e.g., WP3 replication, WP4 Dissemination & Communication) and any cross-links (e.g., how a guide supports selection, IR, or policy), so users know where it fits in their process.
- **Helpdesk flow:** the contact form routes requests to VENCAP and Stadtwerke Klagenfurt (STW-AG) for triage (intake fields mirror the Marketplace template), creating traceable follow-ups for replication support.
- **Accessibility & GDPR:** alt-text, descriptive file names, and minimal-data contact handling are applied across the page.

What remains going forward:

The website and Marketplace stay online beyond project end until 2030 to support replication. Newly validated deliverables are promoted from **Draft** to **Public** with a short changelog. High-value materials (Replication Pack, IR stack, PPP templates) are kept current and mirrored to persistent repositories to maintain reliability for cities, utilities, founders, and investors.

The Resource page functions as a **replication starter kit** and a **clean evidence shelf**: cities/utilities can download exactly what they need to run the process end-to-end; founders get clear, investor-grade templates;

investors find governance and impact frames; and everyone benefits from a consistent structure, status transparency, and long-term links.

2.2. Discussion forum

As part of the project, a stakeholder platform was planned to track the CE project's progress and ensure alignment with the needs of all target groups. The aim was to provide an open communication channel between entrepreneurs, investors, regional authorities, policymakers, utilities, and the public, forming a community of practice to share best practices and co-create knowledge for implementation. The platform was expected to contribute to education, policymaking, and sustainability outcomes. A stakeholder-needs analysis was planned to support adoption, and the platform was aimed to be demonstrated in the Klagenfurt case for subsequent replication across Europe.

Activities and deviations

The platform described in the proposal was **developed and deployed** as planned ([InvestCEC - Replicable model for local circular economy projects](#)). Its design, specifications, and functionality are fully documented in **D2.2 (submitted)**. However, during the consortium meeting in Valladolid (February 2024), partners agreed to discontinue this **stand-alone forum**. The decision was based on the following considerations:

- a) The traditional forum concept is no longer competitive compared with modern social media channels and creates high onboarding friction.
- b) Actual engagement was negligible, reflecting diverse stakeholder priorities, limited time availability, trust barriers, and a general reluctance to create new accounts in an already saturated digital environment.

Replacement approach: Fit-for-Purpose Communication

To achieve the original objectives, while avoiding the drawbacks of a separate forum, the consortium implemented an integrated multi-channel approach consisting of the following parts:

- **LinkedIn Discussion Stream:** Curated by partners and focused on short, practitioner-oriented threads (e.g., selection, investment readiness, PPP/off-take, funding pointers), linking back to the Resource page and the Marketplace and related to the topics discussed during the thematic webinars.
- **Website Contact and Helpdesk intake:** A light GDPR-compliant contact flow routing case-specific questions to relevant partners (Venionaire Capital and Stadtwerke Klagenfurt) for triage and documented follow-up. The intake fields matched the Marketplace profile, which resulted in requests being rapidly scoped.

- **Webinars & recordings** providing interactive sessions offering real-time exchange and on-demand training, with direct links to referenced templates and tools.
- **Newsletter cadence:** regular updates highlight new resources, events, and calls to action, driving qualified traffic to the Resource page. **Marketplace as an Action Anchor**, replaced generic forum threads with standardised solution profiles that invited targeted dialogue (e.g., pilot scoping or investment readiness support).

Posts prioritise concise “what changed and why” updates over long prompts and always point to a relevant guide/template. No forum accounts are required; contact flows follow a **minimal-data, GDPR-compliant** approach.

How the migration worked in practice:

- Website ↔ LinkedIn embedding: GIE embedded the LinkedIn feed on the project website and cross-links posts to relevant guides and templates. Each major resource page linked back to the associated discussion thread to keep questions and answers visible and connected to the content.
- Helpdesk Intake: a short contact form routes case-specific requests to the relevant partners for triage. The intake fields mirrored the Marketplace profile, creating traceable hand-offs to coaching or pilot scoping.
- Newsletter Cadence: periodic digests summarized new tools, events, and calls to action, driving qualified traffic back to the Resource page and Marketplace.
- Data & Governance: no user accounts were required. The contact flow follows a minimal-data, GDPR-compliant process.

Outcome: This pivot has delivered higher engagement with lower friction: more qualified interactions via LinkedIn, more actionable requests through the helpdesk, and stronger conversion from posts and webinars into resource downloads and pilot/IR follow-ups. The original objectives, including community exchange, knowledge sharing, and practical support for implementation, are now achieved through channels stakeholders already use, while the developed forum remains documented in the project record for completeness.

2.3. Professional articles

In the News and Events section, several articles were published to invite stakeholders to explore key deliverables relevant to InvestCEC's target groups. These included the Replication Plan, which outlines the initial steps in replicating the InvestCEC model and provides a structured framework for adapting it to diverse urban and regional settings.

Additionally, the Mid-term Project Policy Recommendations offered EU and local/regional policymakers' practical recommendations to unlock circular economy financing in cities and regions, drawing on the experiences of InvestCEC consortium partners.

The deliverable on circular economy investment addressed financial barriers and suggested measures to overcome them, focusing on strategies for reusing, recycling, and regenerating materials to reduce waste and optimize resource use.

The article 'Generational perceptions and perspectives on the circular economy' analyzed how different generations understand and adopt the circular economy: baby boomers show less familiarity, Generation X takes a practical approach, millennials see it as a sustainable opportunity, and Generation Z stands out for its environmental and digital commitment. The study identifies specific motivations and barriers to driving the transition to a more circular model.

Two further articles produced by Enspire highlight key insights from recent project activities:

- ***Engaging Communities in Circular Economy: Strategies for Success*** explores how citizen participation and stakeholder collaboration are essential to implementing circular economy initiatives at the local level. The article showcases approaches for increasing awareness, fostering behavioral change, and building trust to ensure the long-term sustainability of circular models.
- ***Digital Solutions for Circular Economy: Leveraging Technology in Urban Settings*** examined how digital innovation, such as data platforms, smart sensors, and AI tools, can enhance resource efficiency, monitor material flows, and support evidence-based decision-making for circular urban management.

Together, these publications demonstrate InvestCEC's integrated approach that combines policy, finance, technology, and community engagement to accelerate the transition toward a more circular and sustainable economy in European cities and regions: [InvestCEC articles](#).

2.4. Case-specific lab

The **Case-Specific Lab** operationalises one-to-one replication support for cities, regions, utilities, and founders. It sits within the **Replication** area of the InvestCEC website and offers a structured pathway for stakeholders to raise case-specific questions (e.g., selection design, investment-readiness gaps, PPP/off-take and permitting), receive targeted guidance, and access the exact templates and guides they need.

Originally conceived as a standalone “lab” space, the feature has instead been implemented as a **lightweight helpdesk intake**, integrated into the website and discussion channels, replacing the need for a separate portal. This approach removes account-creation friction while preserving traceability and quality control.

To ensure replication efforts continue beyond the project's completion, the case-specific lab form was simplified and replaced with a contact form that includes the details of Venionaire Capital and Stadtwerke Klagenfurt. This enabled users to directly connect with the appropriate stakeholders—whether they are seeking funding and investment opportunities or aiming to establish strategic partnerships with Klagenfurt.

2.5. Thematic webinars

As part of the dissemination activities and the knowledge, confidence and capacity building activities, G!E has coordinated a series of four thematic online webinars.

Activities:

[Webinar #1 Recap: Empowering Entrepreneurs for Investment Success](#)

On April 11, 2024, InvestCEC held the first webinar in its series, titled "Empowering Entrepreneurs for Investment Success." The session, conducted virtually via Zoom, lasted one and a half hours and provided a valuable opportunity for entrepreneurs and stakeholders in the circular economy to connect and exchange knowledge.

The session began with a welcome and introduction by G!E and Enspire, providing an overview and outlining the agenda for the discussion. The agenda included:

- **Uffe Bundgaard-Jørgensen** from G2G delivered a presentation that introduced the InvestCEC setup and offered strategies for addressing funding challenges in circular economy businesses. He highlighted how entrepreneurs can navigate funding obstacles and develop strategies to meet investor expectations
- **Tommaso Buso** from Bankers without Boundaries followed with a session that highlighted how the DEFINITE-CCRI project supports circular economy initiatives by providing specialised project development assistance to help secure investment.

The webinar also included a Q&A session led by Enspire, allowing participants to exchange ideas and ask the speakers about key challenges faced by early-stage circular economy businesses and strategies to overcome them. The discussion also covered how start-ups can build solid, long-term financial plans to present to investors. Overall, the webinar played a valuable role in enhancing dialogue around investment readiness in the circular economy and provided useful insights for all participants.

Webinar #2 Recap: Breaking Down Financial Barriers in the Circular Economy

Joseph Hurtado from MAT started the session by welcoming participants with a brief introduction to InvestCEC and an outline of the session's objectives, providing a focus for the discussions ahead.

Following this, Jorge Calvo Presa from CARTIF began with a presentation on strategies for overcoming financial barriers in the circular economy. The event then featured presentations from various regions, providing a variety of perspectives and solutions.

- **Sabine Herrmann** represented the City of Hamburg and provided insights on the "Strategic Framework for Financial Schemes".
- **Daniel Gerdes** from OOWV – Water Association of Oldenburg-Ostfriesland discussed "Optimising Rainwater Use" in North-West Germany.
- **Kostas Karamarkos** from the Municipal District Heating Enterprise of the Wider Area of Amyntaio (DETEPA) presented "Decarbonisation and Post-Lignite Transition" efforts in West Macedonia.
- **Rosa Onofre** from CCDRA – Alentejo Regional Coordination and Development Commission explored "Circular Agri-food Business Models" in Alentejo.

The webinar finished with an interactive session, where speakers and attendees had a chance to discuss and ask questions, helping to clarify points and consider possible collaborations.

Webinar #3 Recap: Financing the Circular Future

On **November 26, 2024**, InvestCEC convened its third webinar, "Financing the Circular Future," a 90-minute online session focused on mobilising private and public capital for circular projects and structuring deals from pilot → proof → scale.

After a short introduction, the programme featured:

- **Berthold Baurek-Karlic (VENCAP)**, outlining strategies for launching and managing a circular-economy-dedicated investment fund, including the dual-rail InvestCEC approach (EuVECA/AIF blueprint plus venture-partnership co-investments) and what investors expect from founders and utilities, such as clear KPI framing, early off-take signals, and permitting readiness.

- **Günther Dobrauz-Saldapenna (exelixis capital AG)**, providing an investor's perspective on identifying "true" circular opportunities and positioning CE within a diversified portfolio.
- **Emma Pipó Ollé (BioBoost / Inveniam Group)**, sharing regional cases from Catalonia on accelerating and financing bio-based circular initiatives, showing how ecosystem orchestration shortens time-to-finance.

The discussion emphasised the importance of early off-take indications and a credible permitting path to de-risk projects, as well as the need for an investor-grade deck, a driver-based financial model, and a concise impact snapshot as a baseline for diligence. Participants were directed to InvestCEC's Resource page for templates to apply these practices locally.

[Webinar #4: Fostering Replication & Policy Change - Unlocking Funding for Circular Economy](#)

On **December 5, 2024**, InvestCEC held the fourth webinar, "Fostering Replication & Policy Change - Unlocking Funding for the Circular Economy," a 90-minute online session dedicated to translating demonstration lessons into city-ready practice and aligning them with enabling policy and funding instruments.

The session featured:

- **Giorgio Alessandro (Greenovate! Europe) – InvestCEC case and InvestCEC mid-term Policy Recommendations:** how replication assets (needs → selection → IR → pilot) and the Marketplace help cities build bankable pipelines. Participants were also engaged through an interactive poll to vote on InvestCEC recommendations.
- **Elisa Gambuzzi (CETENMA/HOOP)**, discussing regulatory considerations and **Project Development Assistance**, explaining what cities must prepare to reach the capital-seeking stage and how to structure Project Development Assistance effectively.
- **Lorenzo Valeriani (META Group / CircularInvest)**, outlining investor-readiness pathways from the CircularInvest project, including how to present risk/return, align KPIs and impact, and standardise documentation for faster diligence.

The Q&A reinforced that cities linking policy goals to transparent selection rubrics and publishing pilot Participants were encouraged to use shared templates, address regulatory and market barriers early, and leverage CCRI peer learning. Attendees were also directed to the Replication Pack, policy briefs, and Marketplace entries for immediate next steps.

[InvestCEC and Resource Policy Workshop Recap: Addressing Current Barriers to Circular Investment](#)

On **April 3, 2025**, InvestCEC and the **RESOURCE** project co-hosted an online policy workshop focused on accelerating circular-economy investment by tackling regulatory and market barriers and shaping actionable policy solutions. Over two hours, speakers presented draft policy recommendations, shared best practices from both projects, and engaged participants in interactive discussions to refine proposals for EU and regional implementation.

The programme featured contributions from Lucie Blondel (DG Research & Innovation, European Commission), Marco Musso (European Environmental Bureau), Chema Pina (aptki global partners), Katarzyna Balucka-Debska (Climate-KIC), and Askar Sheibani (COMTEK).

The session built on InvestCEC's midterm policy brief and highlighted five priorities for EU policymakers: pricing externalities; expanding the scope of the EU Circular Taxonomy; advancing circular indicators and labelling; promoting new valuation tools for CE; and communicating non-environmental benefits of circularity. A full recording is available.

2.6. Replication Guides

Available for download: [Resources](#) | [InvestCEC](#)

Policy Recommendations (final policy brief): This brief distils the enabling policies that accelerate circular investments at city and regional level. It clarifies how to incorporate outcome-based procurement, quality- and circularity-weighted award criteria (beyond lowest price), innovation-friendly procedures (e.g., competitive dialogue, innovation partnerships), as well as targeted de-risking (guarantees, blended finance) and data/KPI requirements for monitoring outcomes. Replicators can use it as a checklist for aligning municipal frameworks with investor needs, reducing transaction frictions, and shortening time from pilot to scale.

Financial Barriers and Measures Analysis: This analysis maps the financing frictions circular projects face—high capex, uncertain payback/volumes, fragmented value chains—and matches them with practical measures: fit-for-purpose instruments (grants, guarantees, subordinated/mezzanine, revenue-linked financing), PPP risk sharing, staged pilots that generate operational evidence, and investor-grade KPIs for bankability. For replication, it helps cities and entrepreneurs pick the right instrument at the right maturity stage and frame projects in a way that meets investment committees' risk/return expectations.

InvestCEC Guide for Investors: Investing in the Circular Economy: Written for LPs, VCs and corporate investors, this guide explains how to screen and underwrite CE opportunities efficiently. It outlines the core theses, typical unit-economics patterns by solution type, material risk areas (supply, offtake, regulatory, verification), and the standard diligence pack (deck, model, circularity/impact snapshot, pilot plan) used in InvestCEC. Replicators benefit from a common language between municipalities and investors, ensuring that city-ready projects arrive “Investment Committee-ready” with comparable data across deals.

Circular Economy Fundraising Guidebook: This handbook supports founders and SMEs in preparing credible raises for circular solutions. It covers investor mapping, narrative building, traction/KPI hygiene, driver-based financial modelling, round mechanics (targets, uses, milestones), and a practical checklist for data rooms and due diligence. For replication, it standardises investment-readiness outputs across cohorts so ecosystems can coach more teams faster—and investors can assess them on like-for-like materials.

Guidelines on Circular Economy Transition:

This playbook helps cities and utilities design, launch, and scale circular strategies with a clear, step-by-step pathway. It covers baseline and needs assessment (material flows, assets, pain points), sector prioritisation (waste, water, mobility/logistics, energy), goal-setting and KPI frameworks, governance models (roles, responsibilities, PPP options), and procurement levers (outcome-based specs, quality/circularity weighting). It includes stakeholder-mapping methods, workshop canvases, and a lightweight data model for monitoring (operational + impact KPIs). For replication, it embeds the InvestCEC four-phase cadence—needs definition → solution selection → investment readiness → funding pathways—so municipalities can move from plan to pilot to scale using standard templates, comparable metrics, and repeatable decision gates.

2.7. Replication pathway for the Investment Programme

Fit first – selecting replication sites

Replication starts with a pragmatic “fit check.” Prioritise cities/regions that already show circular-economy potential and basic governance readiness: an engaged utility/operator, an innovation-friendly policy/procurement environment, and a shared understanding of priority needs (e.g., waste/water, energy, city logistics). Where these conditions exist, the path from pilot to proof and on to scale shortens substantially—and investors obtain the operational evidence they require.

Toolkit – standardised building blocks

Execution relies on a light but complete toolkit: needs-assessment guides and workshop canvases, standard entrepreneur/solution profiles, transparent selection scoring with decision-useful KPIs (idea/value creation, team/value chain, market/traction), and a practical replication manual that stitches the pieces together. These artefacts reduce transaction costs in public procurement and investor due diligence, create a common language between utilities and capital, and keep projects comparable across locations.

Engagement pathway – from mapping to on-site demos

The engagement flow is deliberate: stakeholder mapping (authorities, utilities, clusters, founders, investors) → focused workshops/roundtables to refine needs and priorities → continuous online interaction (working groups, Q&As, helpdesk) → site visits and demonstrations that evidence technical feasibility and operational integration. This sequence builds trust, shortens decision cycles, and generates the data points (technical, operational, commercial) both contracting authorities and investors need.

Tailored execution – localising models, finance, and procurement

Even with standard components, delivery is context-sensitive: business models align to local price structures and systems; procurement uses innovation-friendly options (quality- and circularity-weighted criteria, outcome-based specifications); and financing paths blend public instruments (grants/guarantees) with debt and equity as appropriate. Close coordination with the city utility ensures early clarity on interfaces, permitting, and indicative offtake or service agreements—key levers for bankability.

Beyond events – continuous visibility for the model and investment programme

Replication depends on awareness and trust. Maintain ongoing PR for the investment programme and the venture-partnership (“virtual fund”) approach—prominently via website and LinkedIn, complemented by targeted media. The aim is to consistently reach municipalities, utilities, and investors, activate new locations, and bring co-investors into the process early.

As a notable signal, a Forbes feature highlighted Venionaire’s investment-programme approach behind InvestCEC ([Is Klagenfurt, Austria, A Model For The Circular Economy?](#)), validating the PPP logic, standardised selection, and venture-partnership pathway as a replicable route from pilot to proof to scale for European cities. This external recognition reinforces the dissemination focus on the right audiences and messages, strengthening the model’s replication potential.

3. Monitoring and Seizing Funding Opportunities

3.1. Calls for entrepreneurs

As stipulated in the project's grant agreement, this "Selection process" involves both recruiting and selecting companies.

These companies are brought into the InvestCEC process by inviting them to address the needs identified in step 1, going through the selection process in step 2 and preparing them for investment readiness in step 3, and potentially considering them as candidates for the InvestCEC investment program.

The first call for entrepreneurs was organised into three distinct phases:

- *Round 1: Entrepreneurs were asked to submit a brief and straightforward online application form. This method was chosen to ensure broad participation by minimising the complexity of the application process.*

In the application, entrepreneurs were asked to provide concise descriptions of their products, solutions, or services, identify their target users or customers, and outline the current development stage of their offerings. Additionally, they were required to specify the resources needed to further develop their company or enhance their products, solutions, or services, such as investment, partners, or strategic advice. They also needed to explain how their offerings contribute to the principles of the circular economy.

- *Round 2: Companies that met the specific requirement of offering a circular economy solution were selected for an initial interview conducted by G2G. These interviews were semi-structured, allowing G2G to take detailed notes that would later be used to fill out a comprehensive template based on the information provided in the application form (screenshots below).*
- *Round 3: A pitch session accompanied in late April 2024.*

The participation overview for the first call for entrepreneurs was marked by an initial submission of 16 application forms. Out of these, 13 companies were selected for the second round (interviews) due to their alignment with circular economy principles, while 3 were excluded for not meeting this essential criterion. From those interviewed, 6 companies were ultimately invited to proceed to the final round of the call.

The final round of the entrepreneur selection process occurred during pitch sessions on April 25th and 26th. Each participant had a one-hour session consisting of a 5-minute pitch, a 20-minute Q&A with the panel (Venionaire, STW Klagenfurt, & Gate2Growth), followed by 30 minutes of internal scoring discussion among panel members.

The panel used scoring guidelines refined iteratively during the call process, adapting conventional startup pitch scoring to emphasise circular economy elements, particularly the level of circularity in idea and value creation and the circularity and viability of the value chain.

Second Call for Entrepreneurs:

Building on lessons from Call #1, the **Second Call** was designed to **broaden reach** while **sharpening fit** to Klagenfurt's utility context and the investment programme without altering the core, transparent process.

Design and Execution:

- **Clearer focus areas:** applicants mapped their solution to one or more of the four corridors: **Waste Management, Smart City Logistics, Renewable Energy, GreenTech & Sustainability**. Submissions described intended **utility integration** and the expected **permitting path**; applicants also indicated any **initial demand/off-take signals** where available.
- **Consistent criteria:** we retained the two-gate evaluation funnel: (1) **Relevance & circularity** (pass/fail overlay) followed by (2) **Quality & investability** (Team & Value Chain; Idea/Value Creation; Market Opportunity). **Utility-deployability** and **level of circularity** remained non-negotiable filters.
- **Standardised profile:** Semi-structured interviews completed missing details from the application; shortlisted teams then presented to a **mixed jury** (STW-AG, VENCAP, and topic specific representatives and experts from the City or University of Klagenfurt).
- **Targeted dissemination:** promotion ran through the InvestCEC website and LinkedIn, CCRI and knowledge-hub listings, European Innovation Council National Contact Points (EIC NCPs), partner newsletters and regional clusters.
- The **cumulative pipeline** comprised **59 applications**. Compared with Call #1, the second wave showed greater interest, but continued to cover a broad range of topics despite the more specific focus — which, based on deal funnel experience, is not unusual.
- **Publishable profiles** have been added to the marketplace, and follow-up discussions with VENCAP and STW-AG were planned for the future, after further development of the investment programme, as some of the start-ups reached out again afterwards. The discussions with selected companies from the deal flow for a potential investment can be continued after the end of the project.

Implications for IR and the investment pathway:

- **IR acceleration:** As Call #2 required corridor mapping and utility-fit statements, conversations focused on **substantive gaps** (model sensitivity, evidence for unit economics and circularity) and public procurement rather than basic framing.
- **Partner review (“virtual fund”):** selected IR-ready cases from the CFEs and VENCAP’s Deal flow will be **shared with the partner funds (Una Terra and Universe Partners) for reviews**. Where there is thematic alignment, the parties explored **next-step diligence**. This pathway was intended to enable future investments – later also alongside the forthcoming InvestCEC AIF vehicle. Strategic co-investors (e.g., an electricity-sector venture arm and the regional Carinthian Venture Fund (CVF)) were also informed for relevant utility-adjacent cases.

Post-project continuity:

Following project completion, VENCAP, leveraging its pan-European deal flow and investor network, will continue engagement with selected and additional entrepreneurs from both calls and integrate them into its deal flow pipeline, revisiting promising cases as they mature (traction/KPIs, permitting clarity, demand signals). Where appropriate, VENCAP will sustain reviews with partner funds and strategic investors, ensuring that high-potential CE solutions are not lost from view while the dedicated InvestCEC fund advances toward establishment.

3.2. Marketplace

The InvestCEC **Marketplace** is live and will stay online until 2030. It serves as the public overview of circular-economy solutions that engaged with InvestCEC and are relevant to cities and regions. It features companies sourced from the Calls for Entrepreneurs. Visitors can browse company profiles and either contact the firms directly via the details shown or use the **“Get featured”** contact form at the bottom of the page to engage with the project team for listing or follow-up.

Each entry provides a concise overview: **solution description**, **location** (city/country), **founded** date (where provided), **company stage** (e.g., Pre-seed/Early/Later), **focus area tags** (e.g., Waste Management, Renewable Energy, Greentech & Sustainability, Smart City Logistics), and **contact information** (named contact and/or email/link). **GIE** manages website publishing and User Interface (UI). **MAT** co-designed the profile standard during its tenure. Cities/utilities obtain a comparable overview of solutions and contact firms directly. Entrepreneurs gain visibility among municipalities and investors; request inclusion via the page form. Potential investors see thematic focus and development stage; follow the contact details or use general project channels.

3.3. Funding identification

Under task T3.3.3, InvestCEC mapped and monitored public–private funding options for circular projects, linked them to typical circular-solution archetypes, and produced practical guidance to help cities, entrepreneurs, and investors navigate financing instruments beyond the “usual suspects.” The work combined a structured landscape note on financing routes with founder-oriented guidance and a deal-funnel discipline that standardises investor-grade materials.

Activities:

- **Landscape mapping & typologies:** we produced *Monitoring Investment Opportunities*, a concise playbook that: (i) categorises **public** (subsidies, grants), **private** (bank loans, mezzanine), and **equity** routes; (ii) explains when each instrument fits which CE solution types; and (iii) clarifies grants vs. investments (timing, risk, match funding, reporting). This paper also highlights recurring gaps (e.g., “valley of death”) and responses such as hybrid/blended finance and risk-sharing mechanisms.
- **Founder-facing guidance:** the *Fundraising Guidebook* translates investor expectations into checklists (how much to raise, valuation logic, evidence of traction, regulatory readiness) and adds CE-specific lenses (direct vs. enabling circularity; Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) trade-offs; impact evidence). This guide provides teams with a shared standard for pitch decks, business models and KPIs during the IR phase.
- **Investor outreach & market feedback:** VENCAP engaged **600+** potential investors and assessed market appetite. VENCAP identify potential anchor routes for a cornerstone investment with institutional investors, strategic industry corporates, Funds of Funds (FoF) and individual investors.
- **Investment-programme bridge:** prepared EuVECA/AIF setup materials and crowd investment rails with CONDA Crowdfunding Austria GmbH and the European Super Angels Club, ready for activation post fund registration.
- **Visibility channels:** calls, webinars, events (e.g., Circular Economy Day; CCRI formats) and the **Marketplace** page were used to surface circular solutions and connect them to relevant funders and city stakeholders; D4.3 captures the cumulative communication impact.

What we learned, especially through the second half of the project:

- **PPP by default.** Closing circular supply-chain loops works best when cities/utilities and private capital share risk and evidence. Potential investors repeatedly stressed that visible public commitment (incl. co-investments) and Incentives are what unlocks private capital at scale. Targeted incentives and guarantees would improve bankability for first-time thematic funds and crowd in private capital.

- **Public procurement** emerged in the second project phase as a significantly larger challenge than initially expected for SME adoption in waste, water, energy, and city logistics: procedures are complex, timelines long, eligibility and bonding requirements demanding, and award criteria often favour incumbents; circular features also increase measurement and verification burdens, raising perceived risk and slowing pilots. In parallel, **circular supply-chain risk** crystallised as a structural investment theme. Compared with linear systems, many circular models operate in thinner or still-maturing value chains: feedstock variability, dependence on reverse-logistics networks, heightened verification and data requirements, and concentrated offtake can all raise volume and price uncertainty.
- **Fundraising reality and market appetite:** New, especially thematic funds in Europe need time; macro headwinds (inflation, geopolitics) dampen risk appetite; competing themes attract faster capital; industrial LP processes are complex. Plan for longer cornerstone cycles while using venture-partnerships to keep validated projects moving.
- **Channels and visibility matter.** CCRI platforms, partner clusters and LinkedIn outperformed generic portals for qualified, financeable leads.

4. Conclusion

Task T3.3 delivered on its objective: equipping cities, regions, and entrepreneurs with practical capacity to move circular-economy projects from intent to implementation. Over the project, partners consolidated a robust resource backbone (guides, templates, replication materials) and ran a targeted webinar series that connected municipal stakeholders, founders, and investors. The Marketplace went live as the public “front door” to qualified solutions, offering comparable, deployment-oriented profiles that feed directly into investment-readiness support and follow-ups with utilities and investors.

Late-stage casework sharpened the focus on two cross-cutting realities: public procurement and circular supply-chain risk. Both proved more material than initially expected for SMEs selling into waste, water, energy, and city-logistics contexts. Pairing financing with procurement design (innovation-friendly procedures, outcome-based specifications, quality/circularity weighting) and de-risking early deployments through staged Pilot → Proof → Scale pathways, standardized IR artefacts, and PPP structures should stabilize offtake and operations.

On the financing side, the investment programme matured with a prepared AIF/EuVECA fund for dedicated deployment, and a venture-partnership (“virtual fund”) model that activates aligned partner funds and strategic co-investors. This track allows promising cases sourced via the Calls for Entrepreneurs and Venionaire’s broader deal flow to potentially progress to diligence and pilots now, while remaining pipeline-ready for the InvestCEC Fund at establishment. In a challenging market, investor partnerships are seen as central to structuring such models and staying ready to catalyse innovation on a larger scale.

The result is a replicable, evidence-based approach: clear needs assessment, transparent sourcing and selection, standardized investment-readiness outputs, procurement-aware deployment design, and financing pathways that work in municipal contexts. With the website and Marketplace maintained beyond the project, an active helpdesk, and committed public–private partners in place, the InvestCEC model is positioned to support cities and regions in translating and scaling circular ambition into bankable projects and measurable impact.